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Research Article

SLEEP BEHAVIOURS AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTSAmal Zahra¹, Tehniat Waheed², Tuba Waheed³¹Sir Gangaraam Hospital Lahore, ²Sir Gangaraam Hospital Lahore, ³DHQ Hospital Rawalpindi.

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Abstract:

According to studies, around one-third of young adults suffer from insomnia (sleep disturbances) globally. Around 32.6% of the patients reported in healthcare facilities with the complaint of sleep disturbance and its associated symptoms.

Material and Methods: This study was conducted in Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore. A total of 89 female students from different classes was included in this study. A predefined questionnaire was served. The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0.

Results: The mean age of the students was 23.89 ± 2.34 years. Regarding the sleep patterns, 63 students (67.74%) responded that they don't get enough sleep during their academic year. Certain factors related to poor quality of sleep were assignments (40.86%), electricity issues (18.28%), irregular ward rotations (16.13%) and hospital duties (12.90%) and commute (11.83%) in case of day scholars.

Conclusion: Most of the medical students have irregular sleep patterns and they don't sleep well. It is associated with their academic assignments, examinations, irregular hospital routines, electricity issues and tiredness after the commute.

Keywords: *Medica education, sleep, emotional intelligence.*

Corresponding author:

Amal Zahra,

Sir Gangaraam Hospital, Lahore.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

According to studies, around one-third of young adults suffer from insomnia (sleep disturbances) globally. Around 32.6% of the patients reported in healthcare facilities with the complaint of sleep disturbance and its associated symptoms [1-3]. Patients who suffer from insomnia for a longer period of time may develop certain complications such as musculoskeletal disorders, anger, mental health, irritability, hypertension, and certain cerebrovascular symptoms [4,5].

Medical students have to go through a lot of academic pressures throughout their career. A lot of assignments, practicals, ward-rotations and hospital duties make them tired early. The situation is aggravated if they don't get enough time for sleep hence leading to a disturbed life balance, poor quality of life. According to some studies, medical students have a poor sleep quality that is way different from health standards and that experienced by modern society [6].

The sleep quality impacts a lot on the life of a medical student. In this case, they might not concentrate on their studies and assignments, might not attend their ward rotations properly and might not perform their hospital duties in an efficient way. This will ultimately impact their professional growth, decision power, and emotional intelligence.

The purpose of this study to determine the sleep behaviors among medical students. This study will help us in finding the root causes of disturbed sleep among them and will enable us to formulate certain

guidelines in order to ensure proper and quality sleep among them.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted in Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore. A total of 89 female students from different classes was included in this study. The purpose of the study was explained to them and consent was taken. Confidentiality of each student was ensured. A predefined questionnaire was served. The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0. The categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, quantitative variables were however presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the students was 23.89 ± 2.34 years. The minimum age noticed was 21 years and maximum age noticed was 26 years. Twenty-nine students (31.18%) from final year, 21 (22.58%) from the fourth year, 16 (17.20%) from the third year, 15 (16.13%) from the second year and 12 (12.90%) students from the first year.

Regarding the sleep patterns, 63 students (67.74%) responded that they don't get enough sleep during their academic year. Thirty students (32.26%) told they get proper sleep despite their hectic routines.

Certain factors related to poor quality of sleep were assignments (40.86%), electricity issues (18.28%), irregular ward rotations (16.13%) and hospital duties (12.90%) and commute (11.83%) in case of day scholars.

Factor	1 st year	2 nd year	3 rd year	4 th year	Final year
Ward	0	0	2	4	9
Hospital	0	0	2	3	7
Assignments	6	9	6	7	10
Commute	2	2	3	3	1
Electricity	4	4	3	4	2
Total	12	15	16	21	29

DISCUSSION:

In our study, 67.74% of the students responded that they don't get enough sleep during their academic routines. Out of them, 40.86% of students related this with their routine assignments and examinations. In a review by Curcio et al. it was suggested that the quality

and quantity of sleep are closely related to academic performance and learning in students [7].

A regular sleep improves the cognitive competencies of students and helps in their memory consolidation as well as getting strong nerves enabling them to handle tough situations. In a study at King Saud University

Saudi Arabia, it was seen that those students who performed excellently during their examinations reported that they sleep earlier in the night and have higher sleep duration throughout the week. This study also suggested that students who have decreased sleep in the night, who sleep late and who sleep during the daytime performed average in the examinations. Similar kind of study was also conducted on Brazilian students as well. This study also suggested similar findings i.e. students with proper sleep patterns performed well in their examinations and daily routines [8,9].

There are some limitations to this study i.e. we included a smaller number of students and secondly who didn't compare their academic performance with their sleep patterns. A study including these factors should be conducted.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the medical students have irregular sleep patterns and they don't sleep well. It is associated with their academic assignments, examinations, irregular hospital routines, electricity issues and tiredness after the commute.

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